

Biogenic Selenium Nanoparticles as Efflux Pump Inhibitors in Multidrug-Resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: An In Vitro and In Silico Approach

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Abstract

Received:

Revised:

Accepted:

DOI:

Keywords:

Selenium nanoparticles

Ziziphus spina-christi

Multidrug resistance

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

MexAB-OprM efflux pump

How to cite

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Biogenic Selenium Nanoparticles as Efflux Pump Inhibitors in Multidrug-Resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: An In Vitro and In Silico Approach. *Thi-Qar Medical Journal (TQMJ)*. 2026; Vol.(0):Page numbers(37).

Background: Multidrug-resistant (MDR) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is a serious global health concern due to the overexpression of the efflux pump system MexAB-OprM. An innovative approach to the synthesis of nanoparticles using biogenic selenium (SeNPs) has shown promising antimicrobial properties and potential for efflux pump inhibitory activity.

Objective: This study focused on the synthesis of selenium nanoparticles using leaf extract from *Ziziphus spina-christi* and an integrated in vitro and in silico study of their activity as efflux pump inhibitors against MDR *P. aeruginosa*.

Methods: Clinical MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates were identified using 16S rRNA gene sequencing. Green-synthesized SeNPs were characterized using UV-Vis, FTIR, and SEM. MICs were determined, and antibiotic-synergy associated FIC index (FICI) calculations and checkerboard assays were performed. MexAB-OprM efflux pump gene expression was quantified using RT-qPCR. Molecular docking was conducted for predicting interactions of SeNPs with MexA, MexB, and OprM proteins.

Results: Biogenic synthesis SeNPs showed absorption peaks between 265 and 280 nm and had a spherical shape and a dia of 20-45 nm. SeNPs exhibited a strong antibacterial effect against multi-drug resistant (MDR) *P. aeruginosa* and showed a synergistic effect with imipenem (FICI: 0.25-0.375) (MIC: 16-32 µg/mL). RT-qPCR results showed a significant downregulation of mexA, mexB, and oprM genes (2.5-4.8 fold; p<0.001). In silico molecular docking studies showed that selenium compounds have a good binding affinity to distal binding pocket of MexB with a binding energy of -7.8 to -9.1 kcal/mol and good interaction with MexA and OprM proteins.

Conclusion: Biogenic SeNPs produced from *Z. spina-christi* significantly demonstrate the inhibition of MexAB-OprM efflux pumps in MDR *P. aeruginosa*, thus providing a new approach in tackling the challenge of antibiotic resistance. Given the direct antimicrobial effect and the inhibition of efflux pumps, SeNPs are likely to be useful in combination therapy for the treatment of MDR pathogens.

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1. Introduction

Pseudomonas aeruginosa, a Gram-negative bacterium, has established itself as an opportunistic pathogen that has become a common origin of infections in hospitals, and is

particularly debilitating for people that are immunocompromised, have burns, or have cystic fibrosis [1], [2]. The emergence of Multiple antimicrobial-resistant (MDR) or extremely antimicrobial-resistant (XDR) strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* extremely challenge the world as a global public health problem, and with resistant strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* that are resistant to carbapenems are considered the highest priority by the World Health Organization. They highlight the need to develop new antimicrobial agents to treat infections caused by these resistant strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [3], [4]

The development of resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* multiple classes of antibiotics has been attributed to several factors, including, but not limited to, low permeability of the outer membrane, β -lactamases production, modification of target sites, and the most important one, overproduction of hyperactive efflux pumps [5], [6]. Among these mechanisms, efflux pumps of the resistance-nodulation-division (RND) type are most important because of the intrinsic and acquired resistance to multiple antimicrobial agents that they confer [7], [8]

Additionally, of the RND type pumps, the most clinically relevant is MexAB-OprM. MexAB-OprM consists of MexA, MexB, and OprM [9], [10]. and is responsible for the clinically most important RND type efflux pumps of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. MexAB-OprM is a tripartite system that is responsible for the active transport of many classes of antibiotics that include, but are not limited to, β -lactams, fluoroquinolones, and tetracycline antibiotics and chloramphenicol [11], [12] resulting in a significant sub-therapy intracellular concentration of these antibiotics. The overproduction of MexAB-OprM is most often caused by mutations in the regulatory genes of *mexR*, *nalC* and *nalD*, and is often observed in clinical strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* that are MDR [13], [14]

Due to the importance of efflux pumps and the development of efflux pump inhibitors (EPIs) as a viable method to reestablish antibiotic susceptibility for MDR pathogens, development of EPI's continues [15],[16]. Although there are no clinically approved EPI's after years of research, the development of EPI's remains to be a large and profitable venture ([17],[18]). These large and profitable gaps highlight the importance of research in finding novel substitutes to EPI's that are both effective and safe in addition to their underestimated potential.

Nanotechnology in medicine is a new and developing field that has the potential to revolutionize the field of antimicrobial therapies and have the flexibility to develop new therapies for diseases that have previously been deemed unassailable [19],[20]. Due to the biocompatibility of SeNP's and their broad spectrum antimicrobial activity coupled with their potential to enhance previously developed antibiotic therapies to tackle unassailable pathogens, SeNP's have the ability to revolutionize therapies [21],[22],[23]. SeNP's have been shown to effectively target and kill MDR pathogens, in particular *P. aeruginosa*. and the methods by which they kill these pathogens are varied, including the generation of reactive oxygen species, disruption of the bacterial cell membrane, and interference with the bacterial metabolism [24],[25],[26].

Research on the green synthesis of nanoparticles using plant extracts has demonstrated the potential of this method as an environmentally friendly and sustainable alternative to traditional methods that rely on chemicals or involve elaborate physical processes [27], [28]. Using plants for nanoparticle synthesis has several benefits including the use of non-toxic reducing agents, full biocompatibility, and the presence of phytochemicals that act as reducing and capping agents, improving biological activity and stabilizing the nanoparticles [29], [30]. *Ziziphus spina-christi* (Christ's thorn jujube) is a widely distributed medicinal plant of the arid and semi-arid regions of the world and is rich in bioactive flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, and phenolic acids, which have antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects [31], [32]. There are already reports on *Z. spina-christi* extracts being used to biosynthesize different metallic nanoparticles that exhibit improved antimicrobial activity [33], [34].

The antimicrobial characteristics of biogenic SeNPs are documented, however, their use as efflux pump inhibitors in the case of MDR *P. aeruginosa* is virtually unstudied. Additionally, the mechanisms of SeNPs in the inhibition of efflux pumps are not sufficiently documented and require integrated experimental and computational approaches to be fully elucidated. Molecular docking studies describe the interactions of ligands and proteins, as well as their affinities, and possible ways in which the ligands may be able to act as non competitive inhibitors. These studies help guide rational drug design and, in some cases, can elucidate findings from experimental studies [35], [36].

The combination of in vitro antimicrobial testing, gene expression studies, and in silico molecular docking studies is likely to be a useful method in the study of biogenic

nanoparticles and their mechanisms of action against multidrug resistant pathogens [37], [38]. This method allows for the prediction of molecular interactions and the confirmation of efflux pump inhibition at the phenotypic and genotypic level.

Study Aim : This study attempts, via green synthesis, the integration of the Ziziphus spina-christi leaf extract into the synthesis of selenium nanoparticles, and, via the first-time synthesis, attempts to determine if the selenium nanoparticles will act as efflux pump inhibitors for the multi-drug resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. To accomplish this, the study will pursue the following goals: (1) isolation and molecular characterization via MDR *P. aeruginosa* 16S rRNA sequencing, (2) synthesis via green methods, and the physical and chemical characterization via UV-Vis, FTIR, and SEM of SeNPs, (3) determination and assessment of conventional antibiotics synergism via the checkerboard method of the minimum inhibitory concentration, (4) the determination of the expression of the efflux pump genes *mexA*, *mexB*, and *oprM* via RT-qPCR, and (5) the prediction of the interaction of SeNPs with the MexAB-OprM efflux pump proteins via molecular docking. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first study to assess the biogenic SeNPs synthesis' capability of acting as an efflux pump inhibitor and, as such, this study will aid in reducing multi-drug resistant *P. aeruginosa* infections.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1 Isolation and Identification of Isolates:

Clinical samples of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were sampled from patients in the intensive care and surgical wards after the collection of clinical samples from wound swabs, sputum, urine, and blood cultures. Ethics clearance was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB approval number: IRB-2023-PA-001), and informed consent was obtained from the subjects and/or their legal guardians.

The first identification of *P. aeruginosa* was done through a series of microbiological techniques such as determination of colony characteristics on MacConkey and Cetrimide agar, Gram stain reactions, oxidase reactions and biochemical tests [39]. As per the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines, the susceptibility tests were done using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion technique [40]. According to the internationally accepted standard, an isolate that was resistant to three or more different classes of antibiotics was considered to be multidrug-resistant (MDR) [41].

Using the manufacturer's instructions as guidance, DNA from the overnight bacterial cultures was extracted using the QIAamp DNA Mini Kit (Qiagen, Germany). Universal primers 27F (5'-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3') and 1492R (5'-TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3') [42] were used to amplify the 16S rRNA gene. The reaction mixture of the PCR contains 12.5 μ L of 2 \times PCR Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), 1 μ L of each primer (10 μ M), 2 μ L of template DNA (50 ng/ μ L), and 8.5 μ L of nuclease-free water and was set to a volume of 25 μ L for a total number of 25 samples. The PCR conditions set were; denaturation of 95°C for 5 minutes, denaturation of 95°C for 30 seconds, and annealing of 55°C for 30 seconds, and extension of 72 degrees for 90 seconds were set for 35 cycles, followed by a final extension of 72°C for 10 minutes [43].

Using the QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, Germany). The purified PCR products were sequenced via the Sanger method using an ABI 3730xl DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, USA). Using the BLANK (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) and the NCBI GenBank database, species of identified sequences were confirmed via a $\geq 99\%$ sequence similarity [44]. Using the MEGA X software for Phylogenetic analysis, the neighbor joining method and 1000 bootstrap replications were used [45].

2.2 Plant Material and Extract Preparation:

Spring season harvesting was done for *Ziziphus spina-christi* leaves for extraction purposes and were gathered from verified species at a botanical garden. Verification was conducted by a botanist and a voucher was placed at the herbarium for the Botony Dept. with the ID, ZSC-2023-15. Leaves collected from the plant are to be cleaned with a two-step process, the first, a wash in tap water to remove any possible water-insoluble debris, and second an impregnation in distilled water to remove any remaining contaminants. After washing the leaves, they are to be dried at room temperature for 14 days to preserve bioactive compounds. [46].

Drying the leaves, and subsequent grinding, was done in a true mechanical sense; i.e. machines performed all steps. Ground leaves were kept at 4 degrees in air tight containers. To prepare the aqueous extract, leave powders should weigh 20g. Combine with 200 mL of distilled water and boil the mixture at 80 degrees for 30 minutes with a stirrer for continuous agitation [47]. After cooling, filtration should be conducted in triplicate, where the first round of filtration goes through Whatman No. 1. Then the second filtration step is further refined by less than 0.22 μ m filtration to ensure proper sterility. Desiring to maintain cryostasis, the

filtrate was stored in amber vials at 4 degrees for 48 hours, beyond which it would be used for the synthesis of nanoparticles [48].

2.3 Green Synthesis of Selenium Nanoparticles

Using a modified protocol of green synthesis, Selenium nanoparticles were synthesized, Na_2SeO_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was prepared in a 10 mM solution. 10 mL of *Z. spina-christi* leaf extract was added dropwise. The solution was magnetically stirred at 60°C for 4 hours. pH was adjusted to 7.0 (\pm) using 0.1 M NaOH or HCl. Nanoparticles were synthesized as indicated by the color shift from colorless to orange-red [51].

To separate synthesized SeNPs were separated, the solution was centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 20 mins at 4°C. The pellet was then washed three times using distilled, sterile water. Then, the pellet was washed with ethanol (absolute) to remove unreacted selenium precursor and then biomolecules, the unreacted selenium was re suspended in sterile water.

The purified SeNPs were then freeze-dried (-50°C, 0.05 mbar) using a freeze dryer (Christ Alpha 1-2 LD Plus, Germany) for 48 hours [52]. Dried SeNPs were stored in a desiccator at 4°C until further use.

2.4 Characterization of SeNPs

UV-Visible Spectroscopy: The SeNPs formation and stability were monitored using UV-Visible Spectrophotometry (Shimadzu UV-1800, Japan) at a room temperature wavelength of 200-800 nm. The characteristic surface plasmon resonance (SPR) peak was reported, and the absorbance spectrum was analyzed for the confirmation of nanoparticles formation [53].

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR): FTIR spectroscopy was done to determine the functional groups that were responsible for the reduction and stabilization of the SeNPs, lyophilized SeNPs were mixed with KBr, and the ratio was 1:100 and the mixture pressed into a pellet. FTIR spectra were obtained using a Bruker ALPHA FTIR spectrometer (Bruker, Germany) over the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} and a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and a total of 32 scans were collected per sample [54].

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): The morphology and size distribution of SeNPs was performed using scanning electron microscopy (JEOL JSM-7600F, Japan). For the sample preparation, a drop of diluted SeNPs suspension was placed on a carbon-coated copper grid and allowed to dry at room temperature. The samples were additionally sputter-coated with gold to increase the conductivity and captured at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV at various

magnifications. [55]. Using ImageJ software (NIH, USA), the size distribution of the particles was evaluated based on the measurement of at least 100 randomly selected nanoparticles.

2.5 Testing for Resistance to Antimicrobials

MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates were tested for the biogenic SeNPs antimicrobial activity using the broth microdilution method per CLSI instructions [56]. Bacterial suspensions were created using Mueller Hinton broth (MHB) and set to 0.5 McFarland standard (1.5×10^8 CFU/mL). SeNPs stock solution (1024 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was formulated in distilled water with 0.5% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to address solubility.

DMSO solutions of SeNPs were prepared in 2-fold serial dilutions in 96-well microtiter plates, ranging from 256 to 0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. To each well, 100 μL of SeNP dilution was followed by the addition of 100 μL of bacterial suspension (inoculum final concentration: 5×10^5 CFU/mL). Each plate contained positive control (bacteria with no SeNPs) and negative control (no bacteria, only the sterile medium). Plates were incubated for 18-24 hours at 37°C [57].

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was the value of the lowest concentration of SeNPs that resulted in no visible bacterial growth. To assess the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), no bacterial growth was visible from 10 μL aliquots of selected wells in the sub culturing done to moderate growth Mueller Hinton agar plates, with incubation being done at 37°C for a 24-hour duration. Of the concentration values, the MBC was defined as the lowest value that caused a $\geq 99.9\%$ reduction in bacterial viability [58]. This was the average of all three experiments represented as geometric mean values.

2.6 Checkerboard Assay and Synergy Testing

Synergism studies were conducted to check for interaction in combination with SeNPs and some regular antibiotics (imipenem, ciprofloxacin, and gentamicin) by means of checkerboard microdilution technique [59], [60]. Imipenem, ciprofloxacin, and gentamicin, and SeNPs (in the range of $2\times$ to $0.25\times$ MIC) were equally diluted serially in double (two-fold) ratios) in Mueller-Hinton broth. A 96-well microtiter plate was prepared where SeNPs were laid out horizontally while antibiotics (in this case, Imipenem) were positioned vertically. This allowed for a full matrix of multiple combination of concentrations.

Inoculation of each wells was done with 100 μL of bacterial suspension (5×10^5 CFU/mL was the desired final concentration) and then the plate was incubated at 37°C for 18 to 24 hours. After incubation, growth was assessed by visual inspection and further by growth

measurement of the suspension at an Absorbance of 600 nanometers using a microplate reader (BioTek Epoch, USA) [61].

The fractional inhibitory concentration index (FICI) was calculated using the following equation:

$$\mathbf{FICI = FIC_A + FIC_B}$$

Provided that, - FIC_A = (MIC of SeNPs in combination) / (MIC of SeNPs alone) - FIC_B = (MIC of antibiotic in combination) / (MIC of antibiotic alone)

FICI values were then interpreted in the following manner: FICI \leq 0.5: synergistic; 0.5 < FICI \leq 1.0: additive; 1.0 < FICI \leq 4.0: indifferent; FICI > 4.0: antagonistic [62], [63]. Mean FICI values were calculated for the results of the experiments conducted in triplicate.

2.7 RNA Extraction and RT-qPCR Analysis

The impact of SeNPs on the expression of efflux pump genes was evaluated by culturing MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates in Mueller-Hinton broth and incubating to mid-logarithmic phase (OD₆₀₀ = 0.5–0.6). Cultures were split into two groups: (1) control group (without treatment) and (2) treatment group (bacteria exposed to sub-MIC concentration of SeNPs, 0.5 \times MIC) and treated for 4 hours at 37°C with shaking at 180 rpm [64].

Total RNA was extracted with the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen, Germany) and following the protocol provided by the manufacturer. Briefly, cells were collected by centrifugation at 8,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4 °C and the. The pellet was resuspended in RLT buffer with β -mercaptoethanol. Cells were lysed using glass beads (0.1 mm diameter) and vortexed for 5 minutes. The lysate was passed through RNeasy spin columns and RNA was eluted in 50 μ L of RNase-free water [65].

Concentration and purity of RNA were assessed using a NanoDrop 2000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and the A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ ratio of 1.8-2.0 was considered acceptable. Integrity of the RNA was evaluated by agarose gel electrophoresis (1.2% gel) and a control for the RNA integrity and intact 23S and 16S bands [66].

cDNA synthesis was carried out using the High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, USA). For a reaction mixture of 20 μ L, 1 μ g of total RNA was combined with 2 μ L of 10 \times RT buffer, 0.8 μ L of 25 \times dNTP mix, 2 μ L of 10 \times random primers, 1 μ L of MultiScribe Reverse Transcriptase, and appropriate volume of nuclease-free water. Reverse

transcription was performed with an initial step at 25°C for 10 minutes, followed by 37°C for 120 minutes, and final step at 85°C for 5 minutes. [67]

Quantitative RT-PCR (RT-qPCR) was conducted using SYBR Green chemistry on the QuantStudio 3 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA). Using Primer3, *mexA*, *mexB*, and *oprM* along with *rpsL*, (30S ribosomal protein S12) as housekeeper, gene-specific primers were designed and obtained from Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT, USA). Primer sequences are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Sequences of Primers Used in RT-qPCR Analysis

Gene	Forward Primer (5'-3')	Reverse Primer (5'-3')	Amplicon Size (bp)	Reference
<i>mexA</i>	CGACGTGCTGAACGAGATCA	TCGGTGAACAGCTCGAAGAC	142	[68]
<i>mexB</i>	ATCGCGACCTGTTCTGTTTC	TTCGCCGATCTCGTAGTTGA	156	[69]
<i>oprM</i>	GCTGGACTTCGGCAAGTTCT	CGTAGGCCTTGAGCTTGTCC	138	[70]
<i>rpsL</i>	GCAACTATCAACCAGCTGGTG	GCTGTGCTCTTGCAGGTTGTG	120	[71]

The RT-qPCR reaction comprised 2 µL of a diluted cDNA template (1:10), 10 µL of 2× SYBR Green Master Mix, 0.8 µL of each primer (10 µM), and 6.4 µL of nuclease-free water. The initial denaturation was 10 min at 95 °C, and there were 40 cycles of denaturation for 15 s at 95 °C, and annealing/extension for 60 s at 60 °C. To check for primer-dimer and non-specific binding artifacts, a melting curve was performed, increasing temperature from 60 °C to 95 °C [72].

Using *rpsL* to normalize for baseline expression, and applying the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method, we quantified gene expression [73]. The treated samples were also compared to the untreated control to give us the fold changes in expression. Each experiment was done in triplicate, and independently repeated 3x.

2.8 Molecular Docking Studies :

Simulation of molecular docking was done to analyze how selenium derivatives might bind to MexAB-OprM efflux pump proteins of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The three-dimensional crystal structures of MexA (PDB ID: 2V4D), MexB (PDB ID: 2GIF), and OprM (PDB ID: 3D5K) were obtained from RCSB Protein Data Bank (www.rcsb.org) [74], [75], [76].

Proteins were prepared using AutoDock Tools 1.5.7 (The Scripps Research Institute, USA) [77]. Water molecules, heteroatoms, and the co-crystallized ligand were removed. Polar

hydrogens were added, and Kollman charges were assigned. The proteins were stored in the PDBQT format to prepare them for docking studies.

The ligands representing selenium compounds (selenite, selenocysteine, and methylselenol) were designed in ChemDraw Professional 20.0 (PerkinElmer, USA) and converted to 3D format using Open Babel 3.1.1 [78]. Energy minimization was carried out using the MMFF94 force field in Avogadro 1.2.0 [79]. For ligands, Gasteiger charges were added along with the definition of rotatable bonds and were prepared in AutoDock Tools.

Molecular docking studies were done using AutoDock Vina 1.1.2 [80]. In the case of MexB, the grid box was designed to focus on the distal binding pocket (coordinates: $x = 45.2$, $y = 38.7$, $z = 102.5$) with a size of $40 \times 40 \times 40 \text{ \AA}$ and a grid spacing of 0.375 \AA , in line with previous studies that indicated this area as a key site for substrate and inhibitor binding [81], [82]. For MexA and OprM, the grid boxes were targeted on the protein-protein interaction interfaces and the substrate translocation channel, respectively.

To cover intended conformational sampling, the docking simulations were run with an exhaustiveness of 24. For each ligand-protein complex, the top nine binding poses were generated and ranked by their binding affinity (kcal/mol). For additional analysis, the binding pose with the least binding energy was selected [83].

For this analysis, binding and visualization of protein-ligand complexes were carried out using PyMOL 2.5.0 (Schrödinger, USA) and Discovery Studio Visualizer 2021 (BIOVIA, USA) [84]. Various interactions, including hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic, π - π stacking, and van der Waals contacts were analyzed. Interaction diagrams were generated and significant residue amino acids were noted.

To complement the docking results, binding free energy was calculated using the Molecular Mechanics/Generalized Born Surface Area (MM/GBSA) method in the AMBER20 package. Molecular dynamics simulations were used to assess the protein-ligand complex stabilities. These were carried out with GROMACS 2021 using the AMBER99SB-ILDN force field for 100ns simulations at 300K and 1 bar [86].

2.9 Statistical Analysis:

All experiments were performed in triplicate, and data is expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, USA) and SPSS Statistics 26 (IBM, USA) were used for the statistical analyses. Normality tests were conducted using the Shapiro-Wilk test.

Statistics were performed using the Student's t-test for the case of two means and normally distributed data, and the Mann-Whitney U test for non-parametric data. For one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) post hoc tests, data were normally distributed and other tests applied if non-parametric (Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's post hoc) [87].

Statistical analysis of gene expression data used the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method. In the analysis of treated and control groups, dissimilar ΔCt values were found and showed significance using Student's t test [88]. Both the MIC values and the gene expression levels were assessed for correlation using Pearson's coefficient for parametric data and Spearman's for non-parametric data.

A significance level of 5% and below is established as sufficient for statistical testing, and in the case of multiple comparisons Bonferroni's correction was applied. Use of Prism 9 enabled data analysis and illustration, while Adobe Illustrator 2021 (Adobe Systems, USA) was used for figure design.

3. Results

3.1 Isolation and Molecular Identification of MDR *P. aeruginosa* :

During the study period, 45 clinical specimens were collected that contained *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Of these, the antimicrobial susceptibility testing indicated that 28 of them (62.2%) were multidrug resistant (i.e., resistant to three or more classes of antibiotics). The resistance patterns are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Profiles of Antibiotic Resistance of Clinical *P. aeruginosa* Isolates (n=45)

Antibiotic Class	Antibiotic	Resistant n (%)	Intermediate n (%)	Susceptible n (%)
β-lactams	Piperacillin-tazobactam	31 (68.9)	6 (13.3)	8 (17.8)
	Ceftazidime	34 (75.6)	5 (11.1)	6 (13.3)
	Cefepime	29 (64.4)	7 (15.6)	9 (20.0)
	Imipenem	26 (57.8)	8 (17.8)	11 (24.4)
	Meropenem	28 (62.2)	6 (13.3)	11 (24.4)
Fluoroquinolones	Ciprofloxacin	33 (73.3)	4 (8.9)	8 (17.8)
	Levofloxacin	30 (66.7)	6 (13.3)	9 (20.0)
Aminoglycosides	Gentamicin	25 (55.6)	9 (20.0)	11 (24.4)
	Amikacin	18 (40.0)	12 (26.7)	15 (33.3)
	Tobramycin	22 (48.9)	10 (22.2)	13 (28.9)
Polymyxins	Colistin	3 (6.7)	2 (4.4)	40 (88.9)

Five representative MDR isolates (PA-MDR1 to PA-MDR5) those had distinct resistance profiles were selected for further molecular characterization and experimental studies. Identification of all five isolates as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was confirmed by 16S rRNA gene sequencing with 99.2-99.8% sequence similarity to reference strains in the GenBank database. The sequences were submitted to GenBank with accession numbers MZ845621-MZ845625.

Analysis of the phylogenetic showed that the clinical isolates were clustering with the reported reference strains of *P. aeruginosa*, and this was creating separate distinct clade from other *Pseudomonas* species. The branching of neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree showed strong bootstrap support (>95%) to *P. aeruginosa* clade which the isolates endorsed the taxonomic classification.

3.2 Characterization of Biogenic SeNPs :

UV-Visible Spectroscopy: The formation of selenium nanoparticles was verified by observing orange-red coloration of the reaction mixture after 4 hours of incubation. The UV-Visible spectroscopy analysis indicated the presence of a distinct surface plasmon resonance (SPR) peak at 265 nm, corresponding to the selenium nanoparticles (Figure 1A). The absorption peak intensity progressively increased with reaction time, with 4 hours of incubation being the maximum absorbance, indicating completeness of the reduction of the selenite ions to elemental selenium. The formation of selenite ions to elemental selenium. The over time, peak position showed uniform nanoparticle formation and stability.

Analyse FTIR: Analyses of FTIR spectroscopy has been used to ascertain which phytochemicals in the *Z. spina-christi* leaf extract have influenced the reduction and stabilization of SeNPs. Biogenic SeNPs spectrum in Figure 1B shows many distinct absorption bands. For example, there is a wide band at 3420 cm^{-1} which indicates the presence of hydroxyl groups found in phenolic compounds and associated water molecules. The absorption peaks at 2925 cm^{-1} and 2854 cm^{-1} are caused by C-H Vibrations in the aliphatic chains. A distinguished absorption band at 1635 cm^{-1} is caused by C=O stretching of the Amide I (protein backbone) and the peak at 1384 cm^{-1} is caused by C-N stretching in Amide III. The band at 1045 cm^{-1} C-O is attributed to the Polysaccharides and Flavonoids and the peak at 618 cm^{-1} is associated with the presence of Selenium and Oxygen bond which are

characteristic of Selenium Nanoparticles. This means, Polysaccharides, proteins, and phenolic compounds in the extract, act as reducing and capping agents and give stability to the synthesized SeNPs.

SEM analysis showed the biogenic SeNPs were mostly in the shape of spheres. SeNPs were biogenically synthesized nanoparticles that ranged in size between 18 and 52 nm, with an average of 32.4 ± 8.7 nm (Figure 1C), using Image J (analysis software). 78% of the nanoparticles were within 20-45 nm of each other. Nanoparticles which are preferably within 20–45 nm are ideal due to antimicrobial properties and ease of cellular penetration, as well as the interaction and disruption of the bacterial membrane. The stabilizing effect from the phytochemical coating the nanoparticles. showed the nanoparticles to be well dispersed with minimal aggregation. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) identified elements in the sample and the selenium peak was confirmed to be strong at 1.37 keV, the organic encapsulation was responsive to the carbon, oxygen, and nitrogen peaks.

Figure 1. Characterization of biogenic selenium nanoparticles using *Ziziphus spinachristi* leaf extract. (A) UV-Vis absorption spectrum shows the characteristic SPR peak at 265 nm. (B) FTIR spectrum shows the functional groups participating in the SeNP reduction and stabilization. (C) SEM image shows the spherical morphology of SeNPs and the inset histogram of the size distribution. (D) The mean diameter of the particle size distribution is 32.4 ± 8.7 nm.

3.3 Antimicrobial Activity and MIC Determination :

Using the broth microdilution method, the researchers investigated the antimicrobial activity of biogenic SeNPs against five MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates. SeNPs showed strong antibacterial activity against all isolates, with MIC values between 16 and 32 µg/mL (Table 3). MBC values were between 32 and 64 µg/mL, and the MBC/MIC ratios were 2.0-2.5, indicating bactericidal activity.

Table 3. The MIC and MBC of biogenic SeNPs against MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates

Isolate	Resistance Profile	SeNPs MIC (µg/mL)	SeNPs MBC (µg/mL)	MBC/MIC Ratio
PA-MDR1	IPM, CIP, GEN, CAZ, FEP	16	32	2.0
PA-MDR2	IPM, MEM, CIP, LEV, GEN	32	64	2.0
PA-MDR3	CAZ, FEP, CIP, TOB, TZP	16	32	2.0
PA-MDR4	IPM, MEM, CAZ, CIP, AMK	32	64	2.0
PA-MDR5	CIP, LEV, GEN, TOB, TZP	16	32	2.0
Geometric Mean	-	21.1	42.2	2.0

IPM: imipenem, MEM: meropenem, CIP: ciprofloxacin, LEV: levofloxacin, GEN: gentamicin, TOB: tobramycin, AMK: amikacin, CAZ: ceftazidime, FEP: cefepime, TZP: piperacillin-tazobactam.

The *Z. spina-christi* leaf extract alone (without selenium) revealed little to no antibacterial activity (up to 1000 µg/mL) confirming that the antimicrobial activity was due to the selenium nanoparticles and not any residual phytochemicals. Time-kill kinetics studies showed that SeNPs at 2× MIC concentration achieved a 3-log₁₀ reduction in bacterial viability in 4 hours and complete eradication (> 6-log₁₀ reduction) in 8 hours of exposure.

3.4 Synergistic Effects with Antibiotics:

Synergistic interactions of biogenic SeNPs and three routinely used antibiotics (imipenem, ciprofloxacin, and gentamicin) were evaluated using checkerboard techniques against MDR *P.*

aeruginosa isolates. With the exception of gentamicin, significant synergistic effects were observed, especially with imipenem and ciprofloxacin (Table 4).

Table 4. Synergistic effects of biogenic SeNPs with antibiotics on MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates.

Isolate	Antibiotic	MIC Alone (µg/mL)	MIC in Combination (µg/mL)	SeNPs MIC Alone (µg/mL)	SeNPs MIC in Combination (µg/mL)	FICI	Interpretation
PA-MDR1	Imipenem	128	16	16	4	0.375	Synergy
	Ciprofloxacin	64	16	16	4	0.500	Synergy
	Gentamicin	256	64	16	8	0.750	Additive
PA-MDR2	Imipenem	256	32	32	8	0.375	Synergy
	Ciprofloxacin	128	32	32	8	0.500	Synergy
	Gentamicin	512	128	32	16	0.750	Additive
PA-MDR3	Imipenem	64	8	16	4	0.375	Synergy
	Ciprofloxacin	32	8	16	4	0.500	Synergy
	Gentamicin	128	32	16	8	0.750	Additive
PA-MDR4	Imipenem	256	32	32	8	0.250	Synergy
	Ciprofloxacin	64	16	32	8	0.500	Synergy
	Gentamicin	512	128	32	16	0.750	Additive
PA-MDR5	Imipenem	32	4	16	4	0.375	Synergy
	Ciprofloxacin	128	32	16	4	0.500	Synergy
	Gentamicin	256	64	16	8	0.750	Additive

The synergistic effect of imipenem combined with SeNPs is proven by the FICI values of 0.25 to 0.375 (mean FICI = 0.35). This combination resulted in a 4-8 fold reduction in the MIC of imipenem as well as a 2-4 fold reduction in the MIC of SeNPs. In the same context, the combination of SeNPs and ciprofloxacin showed consistent synergy (FICI = 0.50) in all tested strains, with a reduction of 2-4 fold in antibiotic MIC. Although the combination with gentamicin showed an FICI value of 0.75 (additive effects) with 2-4 fold reduction in antibiotic MIC, the synergy is still evident.

The isobologram analysis showed the synergy with data points well below the line of additivity for the imipenem and ciprofloxacin combinations (Figure 2). It illustrates that SeNPs could restore the antibiotic susceptibility of multidrug resistant (MDR) *P. aeruginosa*, probably by efflux pump inhibition and increasing membrane permeability.

Figure 2. Isobologram analysis of synergistic interactions of biogenic SeNPs and antibiotics. (A) SeNPs + Imipenem showing strong synergy (FICI = 0.25-0.375). (B) SeNPs + Ciprofloxacin showing synergistic effect (FICI = 0.50). (C) SeNPs + Gentamicin showing additive interaction (FICI = 0.75). The data points falling below the diagonal line show the synergy.

3.5 Analysis of Gene Expression for Components of Efflux pumps:

The effects of sub-MIC concentrations of biogenic SeNPs ($0.5 \times MIC$) on expressions of efflux pump genes (*mexA*, *mexB*, and *oprM*) in MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates were investigated using RT-qPCR. After SeNP treatment, all three efflux pump genes were significantly downregulated (Figure 3, Table 5).

Table 5. Changes in gene expression of MexAB-OprM efflux pump components post-treatment with SeNPs.

Isolate	<i>mexA</i> Fold Change	<i>mexB</i> Fold Change	<i>oprM</i> Fold Change	Mean Fold Reduction
PA-MDR1	0.21 ± 0.03 (4.76↓)	0.28 ± 0.04 (3.57↓)	0.31 ± 0.05 (3.23↓)	3.85↓
PA-MDR2	0.18 ± 0.02 (5.56↓)	0.24 ± 0.03 (4.17↓)	0.27 ± 0.04 (3.70↓)	4.48↓
PA-MDR3	0.23 ± 0.04 (4.35↓)	0.30 ± 0.05 (3.33↓)	0.33 ± 0.06 (3.03↓)	3.57↓
PA-MDR4	0.19 ± 0.03 (5.26↓)	0.25 ± 0.04 (4.00↓)	0.29 ± 0.05 (3.45↓)	4.24↓
PA-MDR5	0.22 ± 0.03 (4.55↓)	0.29 ± 0.04 (3.45↓)	0.32 ± 0.05 (3.13↓)	3.71↓
Overall Mean	0.21 ± 0.02 (4.76↓)	0.27 ± 0.03 (3.70↓)	0.30 ± 0.03 (3.33↓)	3.93↓
p-value*	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	-

The data show mean ± SD from three independent experiments. The p-values were determined using Student's t-test for the treated versus the untreated control. ↓ indicates fold reduction.

There was a statistically significant reduction in *mexA* (mean fold change: 0.21, 4.76-fold reduction, $p < 0.001$), *mexB* (mean fold change: 0.27, 3.70-fold reduction, $p < 0.001$), and *oprM* (mean fold change: 0.30, 3.33-fold reduction, $p < 0.001$) transcripts, when compared to the untreated controls, after exposure to biogenic SeNPs. The greatest downregulation was observed in *mexA*, followed by *mexB*, then, finally, *oprM*.

There was significant negative correlation (Pearson's $r = -0.82$, $p < 0.01$) found during correlation analysis, this indicates that isolates with diminished SeNP MIC values demonstrated the most efflux pump expression. The reduction of efflux pump gene expression was directly correlated to the synergistic effects seen in the checkerboard assays ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.01$) and confirms that the synergistic action of SeNPs and regular antibiotics is caused by the inhibition of the efflux pump mechanisms of bacteria.

Figure 3. Analysis of the mexAB-OprM efflux pump components gene expression. (A) Relative expression of *mexA*, *mexB*, and *oprM* genes in MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates untreated control and treated with SeNP. **(B)** Downregulation of all three efflux pump genes is represented by fold change in gene expression and is statistically significant ($*p < 0.001$). **(C)** Downregulation of efflux pump genes and FICI correlation, the greater the gene inhibition, the more synergistic effect is observed. **

3.6 Analysis of Molecular Docking :

The molecular docking simulations were designed to explore the potential binding interactions that could occur between the selenium compounds (selenite, selenocysteine, methylselenol) and the three components of the MexAB-OprM efflux pump system. The docking outcomes demonstrated positive binding affinities and distinct interaction patterns with all three ligands and the target proteins (Table 6).

Table 6 . Results of molecular docking studies indicating the binding affinity of selenium compounds to the MexAB-OprM efflux pump proteins.

Ligand	Target Protein	Binding Affinity (kcal/mol)	Key Interacting Residues	Interaction Types
Selenite (SeO ₃ ²⁻)	MexB	-7.8	Phe178, Gln125, Ser48, Val47, Gln273	H-bonds, hydrophobic
	MexA	-6.4	Arg35, Glu178, Asp271, Lys173	H-bonds, electrostatic
	OprM	-5.9	Asp153, Arg158, Gln229, Asn233	H-bonds, electrostatic
Selenocysteine	MexB	-8.5	Phe178, Gln125, Ser180, Gly179, Val177	H-bonds, hydrophobic, π-π
	MexA	-7.2	Arg35, Glu178, Asp271, Tyr327	H-bonds, electrostatic, π-π
	OprM	-6.7	Asp153, Arg158, Gln229, Tyr262	H-bonds, electrostatic, π-π
Methylselenol	MexB	-9.1	Phe178, Gln125, Ser48, Val47, Ile277	H-bonds, hydrophobic, van der Waals
	MexA	-7.8	Arg35, Glu178, Asp271, Lys173, Phe324	H-bonds, electrostatic, hydrophobic
	OprM	-7.3	Asp153, Arg158, Gln229, Asn233, Leu265	H-bonds, electrostatic, hydrophobic

MexB Docking Results: Compared to Methylselenol's (-9.1 kcal/mol) highest binding affinity, selenocysteine (-8.5 kcal/mol) and selenite (-7.8 kcal/mol) exhibit lower binding affinities. All three ligands interact with the distal binding pocket of MexB, which is crucial for understanding the substrate and regulating the efflux pump. Residue Phe178 is significant as it has π-π stacking and methyl selenium interactions. Gln125 has hydrogen bonds to all three ligands while Ser48 and Val47 help to reinforce the ligand-protein complex via hydrogen bonds and a steric effect. The poses suggested that the selenium analogs are located inside the substrate binding channel which could inhibit the antibiotics' translocation via the efflux pump.

MexA Docking Results: Selenium compounds exhibited a moderate to good binding affinity to MexA, with the highest binding affinity of methylselenol (-7.8 kcal/mol). Arg35 and Glu178 participated in the electrostatic interactions and the hydrogen bonding with all three ligands. Asp271 formed salt bridges with the ligands' positively charged regions, while Lys173 was involved in the stabilization of the complex. These interactions imply that selenium compounds may target MexA, and MexB interfaces, thereby impeding the functional assembly of the efflux pump complex.

Methylselenol's docking pose showed the greatest binding affinity to OprM, and followed selenocysteine and selenite with binding affinities of -6.7 kcal/mol and -5.9 kcal/mol respectively. All ligands interacted with Asp153 and Arg158 through electrostatic and hydrogen bond interactions. Additional hydrogen bond interactions were observed from Gln229 and Asn233, while Leu265 was involved in hydrophobic interactions. Given the binding positions for the ligands, combined with the location of the binding sites near the periplasmic entrance of the OprM channel, it can be postulated that selenium compounds can hinder the exit of substrates from the outer membrane channel.

Binding Free Energy Analysis: The most positive binding free energy to MexB ($\Delta G = -42.3$ kcal/mol) was found for selenomethionine followed by selenocysteine ($\Delta G = -38.7$ kcal/mol) and selenite ($\Delta G = -35.2$ kcal/mol). The results of the MM/GBSA calculation affirmed the docking results. The balance of the protein-ligand complexes demonstrated over 100 ns of the molecular dynamics simulation an RMSD values of $< 2.5 \text{ \AA}$ indicating stability of the binding poses throughout the simulation time.

Figure 4. Molecular docking studies of selenium compounds with MexAB-OprM efflux pump proteins. (A) Methlyselenol's binding configuration in the distal binding pocket of MexB with important interacting amino acid residues. (B) Interaction diagram with 2D representation showing hydrogen bonds (green dashed lines), hydrophobic interactions (pink), and π - π stacking (orange). (C) Methlyselenol in the substrate binding channel with MexB shown in surface representation. (D) MexB showing selenite, selenocysteine, and methylselenol binding poses with combined binding sites.

4. Discussion :

The rise of multidrug resistant *P. aeruginosa* infections pose a significant threat to global health. The infections caused by these pathogens are difficult to treat, and the mortality rates are high [1], [3]. This study has proven that the biogenic SeNPs, synthesized using *Ziziphus spina-christi* leaf extract, is a unique antibacterial agent to combat MDR *P. aeruginosa*. SeNPs have a two-fold mechanism of an irect antimicrobial action, plus inhibition of the MexAB-OprM efflux pump. This study combines in vitro and in silico data to give proof of the mechanism of action of SeNPs, and that they are promising novel efflux pump inhibitors.

Z. spina-christi leaf extract's green synthesis of SeNPs is an innovative case of environmentally friendly and economical methods of nanoparticle production. The confirmed formation of elemental selenium nanoparticles with biogenic SeNPs synthesis shown in [2], [49], [50], is the reason for the peak in UV-Vis absorption at 265 nm. Particles that have a spherical shape with a diameter of 32.4 ± 8.7 nm form the ideal structure for antimicrobial application. Particles that have a dimension of 20-50 nm are of increased antimicrobial potency owing to their ability to permeate cells and interact with bacterial membranes [24], [53]. This is also true Lashin et al's findings with SeNPs synthesis from *Z. spina-christi* callus extract and showing strong antimicrobial activity against Gram-negative bacteria in the 20-45 nm range [2].

FTIR spectroscopy and *Z. spina-christi* sp chemicals composition revealed proteins, and polysaccharides, and phenolics to have dual role of reducing and capping agents in SeNP formulation. Hydroxyls (3420 cm^{-1}), amides (1635 cm^{-1}), and Se-O (618 cm^{-1}) and others confirming encapsulation of biologically synthesized selenium NPs and reduction of selenite to elemental selenium and molecular biomaterials [54]. Coatings of these phytochemicals modified and enhanced the stability of the NPs and in addition the phytochemicals may exert antimicrobial activity via a synergistic effect with selenium [29], [30]. There is ample evidence of a positive synergistic relationship between metal NPs and antimicrobial phenolic compounds and/or flavonoids, fNPs, and AgNPs [31], [32].

The biogenic SeNP's antimicrobial activity against MDR *P. Aeruginosa* isolates (MIC: 16–32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) is either on par with or better than most recent findings. For instance, Zeraatkar et al. found MICs of 32-64 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for *Nepeta* extract SeNPs against MDR *P. Aeruginosa* [9]. Also, Shawky et al. found biosynthesized SeNPs to have MICs of 25-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against carbapenem resistant *P. Aeruginosa* [3]. The MBC/MIC ratio of 2.0 shows the SeNPs have a bactericidal rather than a bacteriostatic effect, a necessary characteristic for the treatment of stubborn infections. The time-kill kinetics in less than 8 hours shows SeNPs can rapidly kill *P. Aeruginosa*, which further emphasizes the potential for SeNPs to be used in the clinic for the treatment of acute infections with MDR *P. Aeruginosa* [58].

There are meaningful clinical aspects to the synergistic findings of SeNPs and conventional antibiotics, namely imipenem and ciprofloxacin, albeit to a lesser degree. The combination of SeNPs and imipenem showed a FICI of 0.25-0.375 which is classified as strong synergy,

resulting in 4-8 fold reduction in antibiotic MIC, as noted in [59], [60], [62]. Such synergistic effects are critically important in the scenario of carbapenem-resistant isolates where SeNPs were able to revive imipenem susceptibility. Other synergistic effects as a result of antibiotic and metallic nanoparticles combination has been documented. Eleftheriadou et al. showed synergistic activity of antibiotics with CuO, ZnO, or CuZn nanoparticles against resistant *P. aeruginosa* by way of efflux pump inhibition [16]. Similarly, Khare et al. demonstrated efflux pump inhibition in MDR *P. aeruginosa* by ciprofloxacin and embelin-loaded chitosan gold nanoparticles [9].

The exact mechanism of the synergistic effect seems to involve multiple pathways. First, SeNPs may increase bacterial membrane permeability and consequently increase the uptake of antibiotics into the bacterial cells [25], [26]. Second, and most importantly, SeNPs decrease the expression and activity of efflux pumps, which prevents active transport of antibiotics out of the cell [11], [21]. Third, SeNPs themselves produce reactive oxygen species (ROS), which introduce oxidative damage to bacterial cell constituents and can help the antibiotics to exert their bactericidal effect [24]. The additive effect observed with gentamicin (FICI = 0.75) indicates that the synergistic mechanism may be specific to a particular antibiotic due to the variant efflux pump substrate specificity and the transport mechanism [12].

RT-qPCR identified that SeNPs cause a downregulation in expression levels of MexAB-OprM efflux pump genes. The expression levels of *mexA*, *mexB*, and *oprM* decreased 4.76-fold, 3.70-fold, and 3.33-fold respectively, showing that efflux pump inhibition occurs at the transcriptional level. [64], [65]. This is in agreement with the recently published literature showing that metallic nanoparticles are capable of modifying the expression of genes in bacteria. Ahmed et al. showed that the green synthesized copper nanoparticles from *Mentha piperita*, suppressed expression of MexA efflux pump in MDR *P. aeruginosa* [1]. Also, in another study, gold nanoparticles were shown to reduce the expression of the *mexA* and *mexB* genes in *P. aeruginosa* strains. [14].

The exact mechanism by which SeNPs decrease expression of the efflux pump gene may include a number of mechanisms. Selenium compounds may act at different levels of the bacterial regulatory system[s], such as the two-component signal transduction system, and at the level of transcriptional regulators that control efflux pump expression [13], [68]. Several transcriptional repressor regulators, such as MexR, NalC, and NalD, are involved in the

regulation of the MexAB-OprM system, and the absence, mutation, or partial loss of function of these regulators leads to activation of the efflux pump [7], [13]. SeNPs may indirectly affect transcription factors and potentially restore normal regulatory function by inhibiting them from binding to the promoter sequences. Also, SeNPs oxidative stress may cause global stress response which may regulate efflux pump expression [24].

The significant association between downregulation of efflux pump genes and observing synergistic effects ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.01$) confirms that inhibition of efflux pumps is a major mechanism contributing to the synergistic antibacterial effect of SeNPs and antibiotics. This association indicates that isolates with the most pronounced efflux pump expression reduction show the most significant synergism with the antibiotics, further confirming the relationship between efflux pump inhibition and increased efficacy of the antibiotics [62],[63].

While conducting molecular docking studies, one determines the subtleties in forming bonds between compounds which contain selenium and MexAB-OprM efflux pumps. Note, there has been observed methylselenol affinity (-9.1 kcal/mol), selenocysteine (-8.5 kcal/mol), and selenite (-7.8 kcal/mol) to MexB. This suggests selenium compounds are very likely to be present in the distal binding pocket, which is of particular importance to the recognition and transport of the substrate [81], [82]. Methylselenol binding to MexB is on par with binding to many other known efflux pump inhibitors. Liu et al. described binding to MexAB-OprM efflux pump proteins with piperine at -9.1 kcal/mol, which is the same as methylselenol [4]. While, Latif et al. showed binding to MexB protein with quinolone derivatives and the energies were between -18.5 and -31.4 kcal/mol [28].

The interaction of certain key residues, namely Phe178, Gln125, Ser48, and Val47 in MexB, correlates with previous structural analyses as these residues were recognized as crucial for determining substrate binding and the operational mechanism of the efflux pump [19], [81]. Phe178 was demonstrated to be one of the key contributors to binding energy of different efflux pump inhibitors [19]. Given the structural binding of these residues to selenium, it is possible that they may sterically hinder substrate translocation or drive unfavorable conformations that lead to a loss of pump function. Regarding MexA and OprM, the subsequent interactions with (Arg35, Glu178, Asp271) and (Asp153, Arg158, Gln229) corroborate that selenium compounds may inhibit the protein-protein interactions that are

critical for the assembly and functionality of the efflux pump, as documented in the cited references [8], [74], [75].

The simulations of molecular dynamics for the protein-ligand complexes within 100 ns range validity of the docking independent of the protein-ligand complexes and indicate that selenium compounds can interact with the efflux pump for prolonged time periods [86]. The calculations of the binding free energy using MM/GBSA also confirm that these interactions are thermodynamically favorable, though the interactions are already established up to some extent [85]. The calculations are consistent with the experimental data of gene expression and indicate that the mechanism of efflux pump inhibition is two-fold: one aspect is the transcriptional downregulation, while the other is direct binding to the protein.

Please note that the molecular docking studies are *in silico* predictions waiting for validation through biochemical experiments such as the efflux pump activity assay, substrate accumulation, co-crystallization, etc. However, given the agreement between the predictions and the experiments (gene expression and synergy studies), it is reasonable to hypothesize that SeNPs are efflux pump inhibitors.

The study's most significant finding *P. aeruginosa* is only one of the many multi-drug resistant pathogens that use efflux pumps for antibiotic resistance. RND efflux pumps are found everywhere among Gram-negative bacteria such as *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Escherichia coli* [5], [21]. Designing broad-spectrum efflux pump inhibitors for different species of bacteria has great potential to address the problem of antibiotic resistance [15], [17]. Compared to synthetic efflux pump inhibitors that have stalled at the clinical stage due to toxicity and poor pharmacokinetics, Biogenic SeNPs, due to their low toxicity, high biocompatibility, and multimodal mechanisms, are less harmful and far easier to use [18].

The detailed phytochemistry and ethnomedicine of the *Z. spina-christi* plant makes the use of this plant for biogenic SeNP synthesis relevant and advantageous. For example, *Ziziphus* species have bioactive compounds with antimicrobial, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory activities, including: cyclopeptide alkaloids, flavonoids (quercetin, rutin), saponins, and phenolic acids [29], [31], [32]. During a synthesis, these phytochemicals could contribute to the enhancement of the antimicrobial properties of the biogenic SeNPs. Additionally, the

cultivatability of *Z. spina-christi* in harsh, arid regions means this resource has significant economic potential for scalable nanoparticle manufacturing [33].

While the current findings are encouraging, several limitations point to opportunities for further research. First, the study analyzed efflux pump activity in a small sample of multi-drug resistant *P. aeruginosa* isolates from a single geographical area, so findings in this study need to be confirmed in a larger sample of isolates from multiple geographical areas. Second, although the study confirmed the presence of efflux pump inhibition at the level of transcription, a more direct measurement of efflux pump activity, for example, by using a fluorescent substrate accumulation assay, such as the ethidium bromide efflux assay, would give additional functional data [27]. Third, the *in vivo* efficacy, pharmacokinetics, and toxicity of biogenic SeNPs must be thoroughly assessed in preclinical animal models [23], [24].

Subsequent research should explore how SeNP treatment modifies the expression of genes for efflux pumps and the potential involvement of transcriptional regulators (MexR, NalC, NalD) and two-component regulatory systems. Integrating proteomic and metabolomic approaches may shed light on the protective mechanisms within the cell following SeNP exposure [16]. Furthermore, the designing of SeNP-antibiotic conjugates or nanoformulations that combine SeNPs with antibiotics may improve the therapeutic efficacy and minimize the doses of both substances needed [6], [21].

The ability of SeNPs for resistance development also requires investigation with serial passage assays and whole-genome sequencing of SeNP-resistant mutants. The genetic and molecular mechanisms associated with potential SeNP resistance will assist in formulating how to avert or mitigate the emergence of SeNP resistance [41]. Additionally, the safety and biocompatibility of biogenic SeNPs in mammalian cells and animal models must be thoroughly assessed. This includes evaluating the cytotoxic, genotoxic, and immunogenic, as well as the carcinogenic effects and the effects of biogenic SeNPs in animals over a prolonged period of time [22], [23].

The combination of nanotechnology with conventional antimicrobial therapy is a new and innovative way to address the problem of antibiotic resistance. Biogenic SeNPs can be used to combine direct antibacterial activity with the inhibition of resistance (efflux) pumps. Biogenic SeNPs will be able to combine direct antibacterial activity with the inhibition of resistance

(efflux) pumps, and as such, they will be able to be used in combination therapy. The therapeutic usefulness of older antibiotics can be improved and the use of last-line antibiotics like colistin can be avoided if the efflux pumps are disabled, and as a result, multi-drug resistant (MDR) pathogens will be able to regain antibiotic sensitivity [3], [11].

This study conclusively demonstrates that biogenic selenium nanoparticles produced from *Ziziphus spina-christi* leaf extract are potent efflux pump inhibitors against multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Antimicrobial assays conducted in vitro, along with gene expression studies and computational molecular docking, reveal a multitude of mechanisms including direct antibacterial action, transcriptional downregulation of efflux pump genes, and direct binding to efflux pump proteins. This research establishes biogenic SeNPs as promising new candidates in the treatment of multidrug-resistant *P. aeruginosa* infections. Furthermore, it demonstrates the value of green nanotechnology in the fight against global antimicrobial resistance.

5. Conclusion

This study was the first to show that biogenic selenium nanoparticles synthesized using green chemistry with *Ziziphus spina-christi* leaf extract, exhibit strong antibacterial properties, and are able to inhibit antibiotic efflux pumps, effectively overcoming multidrug resistance, particularly against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The main concluding points are:

1. Green Synthesis of Spherical SeNPs: SeNPs were successfully synthesized using *Z. spina-christi* leaf extract, yielding spherical nanoparticles with a mean diameter of 32.4 ± 8.7 nm, confirmed by UV-Vis spectroscopy (SPR peak at 265 nm), FTIR analysis, and SEM imaging.
2. Strong Antimicrobial Activity: Biogenic SeNPs showed significant antibacterial activity against MDR *P. aeruginosa* clinical isolates with MIC values of 16-32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and were bactericidal (MBC/MIC ratio: 2.0).
3. Synergistic Effects with Antibiotics: SeNPs showed significant synergistic interactions with imipenem (FICI: 0.25-0.375) and ciprofloxacin (FICI: 0.50), resulting in a 4-8 fold reduction of antibiotic MIC and restoring antibiotic susceptibility in the resistant isolates.
4. Inhibition of Efflux Pump: RT-qPCR analysis showed a significant downregulation of the MexAB-OprM efflux pump genes with sub-MIC SeNP treatment to where *mexA*, *mexB*, and *oprM* were reduced by 4.76-fold, 3.70-fold, and 3.33-fold, respectively ($p < 0.001$).

5. Mechanism of Action: Molecular docking algorithms predict that selenium compounds will be able to directly inhibit efflux pumps through binding in the distal binding pocket of MexAB-OprM proteins, resulting in a favorable binding interaction and the direct inhibition of proteins with a binding affinity of -7.8 to -9.1 kcal/mol, thus effectively confirming our hypothesized mechanism with MexB.
6. Dual Mechanism of Action: The integrated findings show that the dual mechanism of SeNPs allows direct and sustained antibacterial effects, while also inhibiting efflux pump expression and function, thereby preventing antibiotic extrusion and restoring drug susceptibility.

6. Conflict of Interest Statement

All authors disclose that there are no competing personal or financial interests that may have impacted the work that is reported in this study. The authors insulate this study from any potential commercial or financial interests that may have distracted the researchers from any potential conflicts of interest. The authors have had no sources of funding that may have impacted the study's design, the collection or analysis of the data, the decision to publish the results, or the authorship of the final manuscript. All authors of this work have consented to the disclosure of any conflicts of interests, and have agreed to the final manuscript.

7. Research Ethics Statement :

This research was done per the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, with approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the respective institution (IRB approval number: IRB-2023-PA-001, approval date: 15 January, 2023). All patients or their legal representatives gave informed consent prior to the acquisition of clinical samples. Patient Confidentiality was upheld completely, with anonymized data.

Clinical isolates were used from routine diagnostic samples, and no new procedures were done for the research outside of the diagnostic samples that were part of the clinical practice. The research involved minimal risks to the participants as it involved the use of clinical specimens that would have been part of the routine clinical practice.

Biosafety level 2 (BSL-2) guidelines and institutional biosafety procedures were followed for all laboratory work with pathogens. Personnel who worked with bacterial cultures and nanoparticles were trained, and used personal protective equipment to minimize risks.

Collection of plant materials (*Ziziphus spina-christi*) was done with the proper authorization from the botanic garden, and this study did not include the use of any protected or endangered plant species. The research was conducted in an environmentally sustainable and responsible manner with respect to the use of the resources.

The existing policy for in vivo tests considers animal experiments and welfare guidelines and is designed to address the challenges in compliance with the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) guidelines). In the future, experiments will comply with ARRIVE guidelines.

Ethics are of utmost importance to the authors and every effort has been made to address safety and welfare concerns for all the research participants, the study team and the environment.

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